

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTHOOD AND MATURE-AGE ON PRESERVICE TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT AND RELATIONSHIPS

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Abstract - The professional identity development of six 4th year preservice teachers was the focus of a case study which tracked their progress during professional experience over a year-long period in a school-based immersion pathway in Australia. This qualitative case study used an interpretivist methodology to understand the meaning of the pre service teachers' actions, and their experiences and histories. The theme of Relationships was commonly referred to by the pre service teachers in relation to the shaping of their professional identity development during their participation in professional experience. An unexpected finding of this study was that three of the participants, who were mature-aged university students and parents, indicated that the experience of being a parent helped them to engage with students and parents due to the knowledge and understanding they had of themselves as parents.

Keywords - Immersion pathway, Mature-aged, Parent, Preservice teachers, Professional identity, Relationships

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the experiences of a small number of pre service teachers who participated in a year-long professional experience in a school-based immersion pathway. The exploration of the potential effect of age and parenthood as personal characteristics on the development of teacher identity was not an initial consideration of a larger scale doctoral study of pre service teachers' development of professional identity and practice. However, in this short paper, the effects of age and parenthood on the development of professional relationships and teacher identity development is explored.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Relationships

The formation of relationships in a school-based context is critical to the development of a positively evolving teacher identity and is dependent upon the support and acceptance of members of a school community (Caires, Almeida, & Viera, 2012; Darling-Hammond, 2010; Korthagen, 2010). While teacher-student relationships are well-documented in research (De Jong et al., 2014), the focus of studies on these relationships is on in-service teachers and less is known about characteristics of preservice teachers in connection with professional relationships in schools.

2.2 Effect of Personal Characteristics of Preservice Teachers on Relationships

Little research has been conducted on the influence that the personal characteristics of age and parenthood may have on the professional identity development of preservice teachers during their

immersion in initial teacher education (ITE) programs. Worldwide, the profile of those training to become teachers has undertaken a significant shift in recent times (Kelleher, 2011; Weldon, 2015). This shift from students enrolling immediately after high school to a larger and diverse group of people enrolled in pre service teacher education programs brought the researcher to feel that there was a need to understand perceptions of developing a teacher identity from a group of pre service teachers who were older mothers and in their forties.

Pre service teachers who are also parents may seek to train to become educators and work with children because they believe that there are complementarities between their being a parent and a teacher in the future. In a UK-based study by Wright (2013), 33 women who were studying to work in childcare were asked about their perspectives on education. Wright concluded that these women had described their 'drifting' into the profession because of their previous work or voluntary participation in childcare centres. Interestingly, the women referred to links between their family life, work life, and study; and acknowledged that they sought a change of status from mother to teacher, to increase their self-esteem and improve their future possibilities of employment. Similarly, Duncan's (2000) UK-based study of 25 mature-aged mothers found that the 'older' women in this study were able to negotiate strong relationships with their mentors (supervising teachers), whereas the younger teachers described that they felt intimidated by their mentors and a power difference with them. While there was no conclusion made in Duncan's study about whether the older women may have felt less intimidated because they were parents or had substantial life experience, the current researcher viewed this to be an area that was worthy of further investigation.

The influence of family on one’s teacher identity development was significantly referred to in the following studies. In a US-based study by Bukor (2015), three teachers were asked about the influence of personal and professional experiences on their teacher identity development. Bukor found that family relationships, and especially those the participants had with their mothers, had a significant effect on the shaping of their teacher identity and sense of competence as a teacher. The dual roles of being a parent and a university student studying to become a school teacher was explored by White (2008). This NZ-based study found that the mothers in this study had selected to study to become teachers only after they had spent the early years of their children’s lives at home with them; and while some of the preservice teachers’ children displayed negativity about their mother directing her attention away from them and toward her study and attending classes, the mothers strongly felt that they had something of value to share as teachers and as parents, and continued with their studies for that reason.

Little research has been conducted in connection with the professional teacher identity development of mature-aged mothers who are pre service teachers. The researcher felt that the current study sought to explore it as a possible factor for the development of teacher identity among pre service teachers.

III. METHODOLOGY

In the current study, an interpretivist, qualitative approach was used for a case study-based exploration of the pre service teachers’ lived experiences resulting from social interactions whereby they interpreted and made meaning of their own and others’ actions through jointly constructed understandings (Merriam, 1998). Case study was used to develop a

rich picture that allowed for analytical insights of the preservice teachers’ professional identity development, in its completeness and in looking at it from a variety of angles (Stake, 2005; Thomas, 2014). Interactions via a moderated online discussion board throughout the year-long immersion pathway gave participants various opportunities to share their experiences. Thematic analysis was used in the research to identify, analyse, and report patterns of themes within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The researcher made notes of themes not explicitly sought out in the data and used a quasi-constant comparative method of analysis to analyse data from different people over different times (Glaser & Straus, 1967). Furthermore, an adapted form of Boeije’s (2002) approach to using constant comparative method analysis was implemented in order to compare and contrast between online discussion board postings made by the participants. The private online discussion board ran from March to October 2015.

IV. PARTICIPANTS

Six 4th year pre service teachers studying their final year of a Bachelor of Education program at an Australian university volunteered to participate in this study. The participants were aged from 21 to 45 years old and located at various school sites (see Table 1.1). The participants were engaged in a year-long, school-based immersion pathway that started prior to the first day of the school year and continued to the end of the school year. The immersion pathway included 20+ days of voluntary immersion and 60 days of placements in the 2015 school year. Pseudonyms were used for the protection of the participants’ privacy. The researcher had no influence over any assessment or grading of the participants’ coursework or professional experience.

Participant	School	Year level(s)	Age	Number of children	Age of children
Elizabeth	A	4, 5, 6	21	0	N/A
Jacinda	B	5, 6	21	0	N/A
Susanna	C	4	23	0	N/A
Kaeley	D	3, 4	45	2	10 & 6
Raquel	E	1, 3	40	2	14 & 2
Ruthie	E & C	1, 3/4	41	2	14 & 11

Table 1.1 Information of Participants

V. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

As previously mentioned, this paper discusses the unexpected consideration of the effect of age and parenthood as characteristics on relationships and the development of professional identity from the doctoral study conducted by the researcher. The overarching research question was:

1. What experiences do pre service teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession?

There were two sub-questions to explore pre service teachers’ identity development:

a) How do pre service teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?

- b) How do pre service teachers develop professional practice through their immersion in a professional community?

VI. FINDINGS

An unexpected consideration for the researcher was that three of the six pre service teachers (Kaeley, Raquel, and Ruthie) were parents. These individuals did not often refer to being parents in relation to most of their relationships and the decision to study teaching. Kaeley, Raquel, and Ruthie indicated that the experience of being a parent helped them to interact with students and parents due to the knowledge and understanding they had of themselves as parents. Illustrations of how the life experiences of each of these mothers, who were also pre service teachers, contributed to their building relationships with students and parents in school-based communities are discussed in this section. For example, Kaeley described that being a parent helped her to develop relationships with her students. She shared how working through challenges she had with her own children assisted her in helping students in a class:

I recently had to deal with a girl who has learning difficulties which has in turn given her anxiety...I used some of the calm-down techniques I use with my son and we talked through what her problems with the assignment were and we talked through why she was feeling the way she was (Kaeley, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Raquel described that she drew on experiences from being a parent which allowed her to be aware of what interested children which, in turn, helped her to establish good relationships with students in her class:

I have a few boys in my class who play footy and a lot more who watch it on television. My own kids love the footy so the boys [in my class] and I have conversations [about that]...The girls and I have conversations about Taylor Swift, One Direction, and many TV shows on the Disney channel. I am confident in talking to all of the children and feel I am up-to-date with the latest [things]relating to their ages (Raquel, Online discussion board, August, 2015). As with Kaeley and Raquel, Ruthie described how her experiences as a parent helped her to identify more closely with the children in the class. She described that being an older pre service teacher and a parent helped her to connect with the children, and she brought small samples of her life into the classroom to achieve this:

When discussing homework expectations and how to be successful learners, I use my children as an example...I say [to the students]...'I know doing homework is hard to fit in sometimes...we struggle at my house as well but we fit it in' (Ruthie, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Additionally, Ruthie shared how staff at school referred to her identity as a parent in relation to having an understanding of how to support students in class:

[I was asked]to sit in on a Stakeholder's meeting of one of my students. [It was explained to me] that...I had children [so it was] thought I would be able to empathise with the parent during the meeting and not make the parent feel uncomfortable. The parent agreed. She said if I was a younger preservice teacher she would have said 'no' as she didn't think they could comprehend the issues a parent of a child with ASD [Autism Spectrum Disorder] faces (Ruthie, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

These three preservice teachers talked about how their identity as a parent impacted their teacher identity development through their postings on the online discussion board toward the end of the research. The researcher felt that it was probable that this background story was a continued and contributing factor in assisting them to position themselves in their school communities throughout their engagement in the immersion pathway.

VII. DISCUSSION

Age and parenthood appear to have had an impact on relationships that were formed in school communities. The three older women (Kaeley, Raquel, and Ruthie) discussed some of their experiences on the online discussion board about how their dual roles of parenthood and pre service teacher experiences helped them to develop relationships, particularly with students in their classes. This finding is in concurrence with Bukor's (2015) conclusion that the life experiences of being a mother can profoundly affect the development of teacher identity and feelings of professional competency. Interestingly, for Susanna, a single and younger pre service teacher in this study, the bonding of the three women was perceived as somewhat daunting because she compared herself to Kaeley, Raquel, and Ruthie. She seemed to have drawn on the older three ladies as role models who inspired her to grow professionally and be more confident.

There is little available research that focuses on the dual role of being a pre service teacher and being a mother (or parent). Contemporary research has tended to focus on the challenges and struggles these women have trying to balance their two roles (White, 2008). Duncan (2000) found that the extent to which women achieve success in their dual roles depends on the coping strategies they construct to meet the demands of both roles. The three older women in the current research did not comment on the challenges of coping with their dual roles. Yet, they indicated that their roles as mothers provided structure for how they worked with students in their classes.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

Two limitations to the current research must be considered. First, the sample of participants was limited to six individuals. So, only general conclusions can be made from the findings presented. The findings cannot be viewed as being general representations of the experiences of pre service teachers in Australian schools. Additionally, pre service teachers' self-reporting behaviors had the potential to present opportunities for inaccuracies and/or bias to occur during data collection. So, the researcher allowed the participants freedom in writing content via the online discussion board either publicly within the group or privately with the researcher, and this served to minimize any adverse influences of bias and/or inaccuracies in the pre service teachers' self-reporting.

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The mothers in the current study made significant connections to being a pre service teacher and being a mother in both their language and the behaviour they used in interactions with students in their classes. Yet, age and parenthood were not the focus of the current study. So, there is a gap left in the researcher's understanding about teacher identity development specifically for women who are mothers that could certainly be pursued in future research. With the changing demographics for preservice teacher, and beginning teacher, education, this area of research requires further study.

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